

Science Communication Plan of the COST Action 21144 - Superconducting Nanodevices and Quantum Materials for Coherent Manipulation (SUPERQUMAP)

Each Action MC shall adopt a Science Communication Plan including a communication, dissemination, and valorisation strategy, as well as a plan to implement this strategy. The Science Communication Plan shall reflect the MoU in particular connecting to the aims and objectives of the Action. It is recommended that the Science Communication Plan is approved by the Management Committee not later than 6 months after the start date of the Action. It is recommended that the Science Communication Plan, including progress on implementation, is discussed on a yearly basis by the Action MC and reviewed or amended where necessary. ([Annotated Rules for COST Actions](#), article 5)

This template is provided to COST Actions as a support for developing the Action Science Communication plan. Actions can adapt the plan structure and content according to their needs.

VERSIONS AND HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Date of adoption by MC	Notes (e.g. changes from previous versions)	Lead author(s)*
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** The Science Communication plan is developed, updated and its implementation monitored under the overall supervision of the Science Communication Coordinator, and in close collaboration with other relevant contributors.*

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COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology) is a funding agency for research and innovation networks. Our Actions help connect research initiatives across Europe and enable scientists to grow their ideas by sharing them with their peers. This boosts their research, career and innovation.

Communication and Dissemination plan

CA21144 - Superconducting Nanodevices and Quantum Materials for Coherent Manipulation (SUPERQUMAP)

Index

1	About the SUPERQUMAP project	3
2	General aim and target audience	4
3	Plan for the communication of the Action results	6
3.1	SUPERQUMAP visual identity	8
3.2	SUPERQUMAP website	9
3.2.1	Website structure	10
3.2.1	Technical development and maintenance	Errore. Il segnalibro non è definito.
3.2.2	Search engine optimization (SEO)	15
3.3	SUPERQUMAP social networks	15
3.3.1	Twitter	15
3.3.2	LinkedIn	16
3.3.3	Facebook	16
3.4	SUPERQUMAP newsletter	16
3.5	Participation to science events and fairs	16
4	Plan for the dissemination of the Action results	17
4.1	Scientific publications	18
4.2	Organization of SUPERQUMAP Events	19
4.3	Participation in external events	20
5	Plan for the valorization of Action results	20
5.1	Industry	20
5.2	Citizens	21
5.3	Intellectual property	21

1 About the SUPERQUMAP project

Superconductors are systems whose ground state is a macroscopic quantum coherent condensate characterized by vanishing electrical resistance, magnetic flux expulsion and quantization of circular currents. Using superconductors, we can build accelerators for radiotherapy, magnetic resonance imaging systems, trains, electrical power transmission lines, and many other devices. Thanks to carefully engineered materials, applications of superconductors have evolved much more than those of any usual conductor—for instance, superconducting magnets are the game changers that allowed scientists and engineers to build the small synchrotrons needed for proton therapy that is radically changing cancer treatment. Furthermore, small superconducting circuits using Josephson junctions allow measuring the tiny magnetic fields in the human brain, providing completely new ways of investigating brain activity. Josephson junctions are also the basic building block of superconducting circuits, which hold the promise to disrupt computation by enabling the creation of quantum computers at large scale.

Recent years have seen a surge in superconducting quantum electronics, with rapidly rising number of promising devices and systems enabling quantum coherent manipulation and sensing. Quantum computation, for example, requires a perfect manipulation of a large number of qubits - the physical unit of quantum computers. However, this entails major difficulties and is one of the reasons why present quantum computers can only perform a reduced number of operations, as decoherence is not sufficiently controlled in small superconducting circuits. As such, even if we often hear in the news of great advances in superconducting based quantum computers, with an increasing number of physical qubits, this number remains many orders of magnitude below what is really needed. Exploring novel quantum materials and phenomena as an alternative route to improve superconducting devices is necessary now to make a quantum leap in stability and coherence of quantum circuits. This approach, which may enable finding radically new superconducting behaviors, is the main goal of SUPERQUMAP and requires a collaborative approach, joining together efforts and groups all over Europe, going beyond presently available networks and projects.

The challenge addressed by SUPERQUMAP is to harness the results obtained recently in superconductivity and build a collaborative effort to provide radically new approaches to superconducting based quantum devices. In order to do so, we will merge advanced theoretical approaches, modelling, nanofabrication, chemistry, physics, engineering materials science and advanced measurements. At present, there is no network or collaborative effort that favors this cross-fertilization among all the different subjects proposed by SUPERQUMAP.

The Action aims to set-up an open and inclusive network, where discussions involve a varied audience, with a clearly settled goal towards a significant technological breakthrough, but without a priori bias for a given solution. SUPERQUMAP will promote inclusive and open discussions, following COST inclusiveness and excellence policy, and

provide a carefully designed program of meetings, exchanges and common dissemination activities.

SUPERQUMAP network of proposers has been set-up to provide a balanced account of researchers from all over Europe, including 29 countries, out of which 15 are ITC countries, with nearly 30% female contribution, having 13 countries with at least one female member, hosting researchers having obtained 9 ERC grants and numerous grants from former FET-Open program and are present in many projects and activities of EIC as well.

2 General aim and target audience

The primary objective of our communication and dissemination strategy is to increase the impact of the project by disseminating the results, engage target audiences as well as create and maintain the project's constant visibility. In synergy with these objectives, we believe that SUPERQUMAP can have a role in communicating the opportunities of quantum technologies to the general public, to raise awareness and illustrate the impact of quantum technologies on the civil society.

The Dissemination and Communication Team (DCT) will be responsible for the communication of SUPERQUMAP goals and will coordinate the dissemination activities at a consortium level. However, as a wide and effective dissemination of results has been planned as one of the strong components of this project, all partners are committed to contribute.

In order to realize an effective communication and dissemination of the results, maximize their impact and enlarge the community reached by this effort, we identified general subjects of dissemination which will be communicated to several target audience groups (Figure 1).

A. The general subjects of dissemination and communication:

- the SUPERQUMAP project (general scope, coverage, goals, milestones and plans to reach them)
- opportunities offered by the COST action (mobility, conference grants)
- interim results (reached objectives and achievements)
- innovation aspects related to quantum technologies (in an “open innovation” perspective)

B. The targeted audiences:

- Research communities (Condensed Matter Research Community, Quantum technology community)

- Industry (Small and Medium Enterprises working in the field of superconductivity and quantum technologies)
- Educational level (Undergraduated, graduated, PhD students and young researchers)
- Regulating Authorities
- General public

Figure 1. Subjects of dissemination and target audience groups

For each connection shown in Figure 1, the communication will be calibrated following some guidelines:

- Activities need to be carried-out in a timely manner
- Information used must be accurate
- The right audience(s) should be targeted
- Messages should interest the target audience(s)
- Activities should be appropriate in terms of resources spent, timing and expected impact

Special attention will be given to modulate our communication efforts with respect to the different levels of audience awareness, including stakeholders, policymakers, media and the general public. Taking into consideration varying degrees of familiarity with the project and its main topics, the language of communication and the terminologies used will be adjusted at different levels, so that all major outcomes of the project will be accessible also to non-specialist audiences.

Details on the specific approach in terms of communication and dissemination are included in the following sections.

3 Plan for the communication of the Action results

In this Section we will outline the strategy for the communication of the Action results to the general public, civil society, industry and mass media. In the following tables, we list the channels we will use to reach these audiences and the specific approach.

Industry	
communication approach	<p>Openly inform SMEs about the opportunities offered by quantum technologies</p> <p>Engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorization of the project activities and outcomes and multi-stakeholder involvement</p>
target audience profiles	<p>Technology-based SME's in the fields of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Superconducting devices Quantum technologies Photonics Digital Electronic components Other additional ICT innovation areas
Outreach channels	<p>Social Media</p> <p>Website</p> <p>Videos</p>

Educational	
communication approach	<p>Stimulate students' interest and curiosity for the expanding field of superconducting electronics</p> <p>Inform graduate and undergraduate students about the activity of SUPERQUMAP</p> <p>Disseminate the SUPERQUMAP activities in high schools to engage students in research</p>

target audience profiles	Undergraduated students PhD students Students' associations High school students
Outreach channels	Social Media Website Public events Videos

Regulating Authorities	
communication objective	<p>Provide sector-specific recommendations addressed to policy makers, relevant institutions and public bodies at local, national and European levels, to develop national policies and strategic sectorial plans.</p> <p>Report about the general outcomes of the project and innovations.</p> <p>Showcase how our project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results.</p>
target audience profiles	European public decision-makers European Commission National Public Bodies responsible for defining national strategies in technology/science Regional institutions
Outreach channels	Social Media Website Newsletter

General public	
communication objective	<p>Inform the public about the “quantum revolution” and the opportunities offered by quantum electronics</p> <p>Increase public awareness of the project’s objectives and activities, and more in general of challenges at stake in next generation quantum electronics</p> <p>Increase the visibility of the project and its activities</p>
target audience profiles	General consumers
Outreach channel	<p>Social Media</p> <p>Website</p> <p>Public events</p> <p>Videos</p>

In the next Section, we will outline the communication tools the DCT will produce. They will be the main instruments for SUPERQUMAP partners for a correct performance of the communication actions.

The efficient organization of a dialogue with the public requires communicating in the local language. One of the strengths of SUPERQUMAP is the participation of 29 countries (so far) with a similar number of official languages. SUPERQUMAP represents therefore a unique opportunity to communicate the broad importance of excellent research and, in particular, the relevance of superconductivity and quantum technologies in a capillary way, reaching a large number of young scholars and a wide audience in the general public.

3.1 SUPERQUMAP visual identity

The first communication task is the creation of a project logo. A good logo should be simple, in order to be remembered immediately, and, at the same time, able to visually convey the main idea of the project.

The idea behind the SUPERQUMAP logo is that of a “network” where each node is in communication and collaboration with the others to achieve the project goals. The SUPERQUMAP logo is indeed composed by a streamlined network in background and a Q letter in the foreground representing the “quantum” nature of our activities. Three arrows arranged to form a reference system complete the logo.

Two versions of the logo have been realized: a compact one and an extended one, where the acronym of the project is reported.

The main colors of the logo and the font used in it are at the basis of the project web site template.

The logo will be distributed to all the partners to be used in their presentations, communications etc. It will be included in all promotional materials throughout the project implementation and will be clearly highlighted during awareness-raising campaigns.

3.2 SUPERQUMAP website

The project's website, currently on line, is the main communication tool of the project. While the DCT will be in charge of updating the content of the website, all partners are encouraged to contribute items including project updates, scientific results, local events and relevant information, videos, images and news related to project outputs.

The website will increase the visibility of the project and its products throughout its lifecycle. It will be updated to reflect the activity of the project and revamped according to the needs of the project. In addition, it will have links to a range of social media channels which will be exploited for both communication and dissemination purposes.

All partners will link their own websites with the project website, as well as to the forthcoming project workshops. This is a proven method of informing the consortium partner's own ecosystems about their participation and at the same time direct traffic to the project website.

The Web Site map has been designed to offer a complete overview of the project and an easy access to all its activities. We plan to make use of suitable photographs, sketches and charts in order to convey scientific information in a direct and clear way, not only to the research community but also to the general public. Moreover, there will be a main "Wall" promoting the latest updates related to calls, events or activities open to the public. The

website will also host information on how to access the support opportunities offered by the project (ex. support for scientific short term scientific missions or conference grants).

Design of the website is based on the following technical features and characteristics:

- A user-friendly and attractive interface, open to the public of potential users and different stakeholders
- Clear structure, easy navigation
- Optimised for all types of mobile devices (phones, tablets for both iOS and Android operating systems)
- Fully accessible by all users following the requirement for W3C compliance
- Possibility to access and download project newsletters as well as other outputs developed for wide public use
- Facility to share (social media), send to (by email) and print pages, search on the site
- Offer a contact point
- Links to social media channels

3.2.1 Website structure

We list below the sections of the website. Slight changes might be applied, including the development of more pages, subpages or elements if needs arise throughout the implementation of the project.

Website page	subpage	content
Home		Main Slider "Wall" promoting the latest updates Social Networks Widgets Website Footer
About the project		General project objectives and background
	Research objectives	Synthesis of the scientific objectives and list of the work packages
	Capacity building objectives	Synthesis of the impact of the project on the society
	About COST	General information on COST program and links to relevant pages
participants		List of the Action leader positions

	Management committee	Link to the complete list of the management committees
	WG1 Quantum materials	Description of the work group 1 activities
	WG2 New functionalities for sensors and devices	Description of the work group 2 activities
	WG3 Building quantum systems	Description of the work group 3 activities
News and events		Overview of the latest news related to the project
	events	Conferences and workshops
	outreach	Activities aimed at informing the general public
	publications	List of the scientific outputs of the project
Activities	meetings	Info about workshops and conferences organized during the SUPERQUMAP project
	Scientific missions	Info about support opportunities for short term scientific missions
	Conference grants	Info about support opportunities for conference grants (aimed at ICT countries)
contact		contact e-mail and a form for questions and information requests.

Some screenshots from the web site are reported below.

Home page

About the project page

Participants page

News and events page

Activities page

3.2.1 Maintenance and update

The web site content management lies fully under the DCT with the contribution of all partners. The content is regularly updated throughout the implementation of the project.

The EC's logo and acknowledgment of the EU funds in line with the visual guidelines of the European Commission are clearly visible in the footer of all the pages of the web site.

3.2.2 Search engine optimization (SEO)

In order to improve the ranking of our website on the most used search engines, we will use Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) techniques, with selected keywords, key phrases and extensive tagging likely employed by users. We will deploy techniques such as writing keyword-rich page titles and adding description meta tags; include keywords in headers, positioning keywords in the first paragraph of the body text and using keywords in hyperlinks, etc.

3.3 SUPERQUMAP social networks

SUPERQUMAP project will actively use various social networks and online communication channels to increase the impact and reach and interact with a wide audience. Social networks are a powerful tool to achieve a timely communication of the project initiatives, opportunities and results, that is why the Project profiles will be constantly updated to show SUPERQUMAP as an active and interesting project.

Different social media will be used to reach third parties, the research community and to interact with the general public. The communication style will be adapted to the social network used. The social network content will be generated by the DCT with the collaboration of all the consortium members. In turn, the consortium members will also publish the relevant information in their social networks.

3.3.1 Twitter

Handle: @SUPERQUMAP_eu

This channel is used for short news flashes, using a clear and crisp style, not too descriptive or institutional. Twitter allows the rapid communication between professionals, organizations and media. It is a real-time communication tool: it allows tweeting questions and having followers respond within several seconds. Offering only short messages – 280 characters – Twitter is known as a highly paced network demanding frequent activity and updates in order to maintain an active and attractive profile. Retweets enable sharing of interesting content generated by other users as well as the possibility to easily spread messages to a wide audience.

We will actively work on the creation of relevant connections that will contribute to widening the outreach. Twitter will be used to deploy key messages in a short, catchy manner using visual support (pictures, banners, infographics, short video clips, etc.)

informing on the latest developments, news articles, on publication of new documents, disseminating results and findings and promoting networking. Events, such as conferences and meeting organized during the project, will be promoted via Twitter and pictures/videos and/or compelling quotes will be shared during them. At the same time, it will be also used to direct traffic to the website, where the public will have the possibility to explore in more details the activities related to the project. As Twitter is a high-paced social media network, around 3-4 posts will be published per week.

3.3.2 LinkedIn

Being a social network for professionals, LinkedIn allows the creation of dedicated communities and groups to discuss specific topics and spread information to a wide professional audience. In this sense, a group will be created and used to connect with key stakeholders as well as relevant projects and initiatives to build synergies and foster knowledge transfer. Selected articles, news pieces and other communications content will also be shared on this platform. Via LinkedIn, SUPERQUMAP will host a permanent group (membership on request) community to share experiences, events, studies, news and relevant information with peers. The frequency of posts published by moderators in the group is foreseen to 1-2 per week.

3.3.3 Facebook

Facebook is by far the biggest global social network and allows people with similar interests to create new networks, as well as enriching communication by delivering information and providing a platform for community comment and collaboration. It is also widely used by citizens. SUPERQUMAP will realize attractive posts using graphics, videos and images.

3.4 SUPERQUMAP newsletter

A six-monthly newsletter will be published to spread the work of the project. It will be available on the project website and announced using the social channels. The newsletter will synthesize the project advancements and provide links to download the reports and relevant information. It will provide information in a synthetic form, which will be accessible in full version in the project website relevant sections/pages.

3.5 Participation to science events and fairs

Quantum computing has the potential to radically transform the way businesses and organizations operate. It will enable to tackle problems that classical computers cannot solve, such as complex optimization problems, and allow quantum-encrypted communications. Furthermore, it will significantly improve our understanding of systems governed by quantum mechanics, such as molecular structure and chemical reactions and processes of interest for chemical and pharmaceutical industry. Therefore, in the next

years, the impact of this innovative technology on the civil society will be great. The partners of the SUPERQUMAP consortium will participate in several external events (exhibitions, business events, information days, scientific events and conferences) dedicated to the general public, with the aim to communicate the relevance of the next quantum revolution to the general public in an accurate and scientific way. The participation to these events will be announced in the SUPERQUMAP website and, after the event, photos will be shared using the same channel and the social media accounts.

4 Plan for the dissemination of the Action results

The dissemination of the scientific outcomes of the SUPERQUMPA project will be directed not only to the Research community, but also to technology based small and medium enterprises, as outlined in the tables below.

Research communities	
dissemination approach	<p>Provide them with results from SUPERQUMAP activities to establish new basis for research work, collaborations and scientific papers.</p> <p>Participate in the events (meeting, workshops) organized by SUPERQUMAP for collection of results, ideas, new challenges, providing the scientific approach.</p> <p>Build synergies with other EU-funded projects, networks and initiatives, foster collaboration, avoid duplication and maximize impact</p>
target audience profiles	<p>University research groups</p> <p>Public and Private Research Centers</p> <p>R&D groups in private companies</p>
Outreach channels	<p>Website</p> <p>Videos</p> <p>Meeting, workshops, seminars</p> <p>Research papers</p>

Technology-based SMEs	
communication approach	<p>Openly inform SMEs about the results obtained by the SUPERQUMAP Teams.</p> <p>Inform SMEs about the opportunities offered by COST Actions (grants, support for scientific exchange etc) as well as the direct and indirect benefits of them (coaching, network, expertise, etc.)</p> <p>Enhance SMEs participation in SUPERQUMAP networking events in order to build alliances with superconductivity and quantum technologies stakeholders.</p>
target audience profiles	<p>Technology-based SME's in the fields of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Superconducting devices - Quantum technologies - Photonics - Digital Electronic components - Other additional ICT innovation areas
Outreach channels	<p>Social Media Website Newsletters Research papers Workshops</p>

Many of the communication tools described in the previous Section will be, naturally, employed also for the dissemination of the scientific results. In particular, the website will be the main showcase of the activities, including meetings, scientific results etc. To these tools we will add the publication of scientific papers and the organization of workshops and conferences.

4.1 Scientific publications

The research advancements of the SUPERQUMAP participants will be published in high impact scientific journals. Support from CA21144 will be acknowledged in all publications and the results will be announced on the website.

Action publications will be available in arxiv, independent of the publisher chosen by the authors, and whenever possible in open access schemes.

The Action will ask participants to share data, software and hardware whenever possible using github, zenodo or similar repositories.

4.2 Organization of SUPERQUMAP Events

Networking is one of the main tools for the dissemination of the Action activities. Moreover, the multidisciplinary nature of SUPERQUMAP, including researchers from different countries, different kinds of institutions (universities, research centers and industry) and different disciplines, calls for the need of regular meetings, in order to foster their activities within the network to gain full advantage of cross-fertilization. We foresee a rich program of meetings and events, including Schools dedicated to young researchers. We will also exploit the possibility to meet online to organize “mini-workshops” focused on specific topics of interests for the several work groups (WG) of the project.

The progress of the Action will constantly be monitored during frequent meetings of the Management committee.

Below, we list the workshops the Action will organize. Each event is linked to one of the three work groups of the project but will be, of course, opened to all participants.

- Workshops
 - Workshop on quantum materials for coherent manipulation of superconducting states (month 13-15)
 - Workshop on low dimensional and low carrier density superconductors and their applications in sensing devices (month 22-24)
 - Workshop on coherent superconducting two-level systems for quantum computation (month 34-36)

- Online mini-workshops
 - Online mini-workshop of the WG1 (month 31-33)
 - Online mini-workshop of the WG2 (month 10-12)
 - Online mini-workshop of the WG3 (month 19-21)

- Training event (school) during the first year
- A large conference the last year of the Action

The workshops and conferences programs will be carefully set up in order to ensure a balanced representation of all the countries involved in the action, to stimulate the participation of young researchers and, of course, to achieve gender balance. The participation of industries will be encouraged.

The workshops and events will be advertised on the Action web site and through social media channels. The participants will be encouraged to advertise the SUPERQUMAP events also through their institutional web pages.

The Table below shows the scheduling of the dissemination events.

event	4y Action lifetime														
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Q12	Q13	Q14	Q15
workshop															
Online meeting															
School/conference															
MC meeting															

4.3 Participation in external events

To achieve the maximum exposure of the project results, to encourage the involvement of other research groups in the Action activities and to stimulate collaborations, the members of the Action will participate in major relevant conferences and workshops. The webpage can be used to publicize external events organized by Action members and contributions to other events.

5 Plan for the valorization of Action results

SUPERQUMAP will bring together scientists and engineers from different backgrounds, developing research that uses different knowledge and fostering collaboration to avoid duplication of efforts and resources. The Action focuses on excellent science, with a large impact on societal needs. We plan specific valorization actions directed towards both the civil society and industrial partners aiming at creating maximum impact and awareness of the project’s results. It is important to develop tailored valorization tools for different types of target audiences. The most appropriate outputs depend on whom SUPERQUMAP wants to address and at what level.

5.1 Industry

Exchange between industry and academia helps academic knowledge and results flow into industry. Likewise, it gives researchers the opportunity to increase their skills and gain a better knowledge of industry needs. In the next future quantum technologies will have a sizeable impact on the industry, therefore a timely mutual exchange between academia and companies is much needed. The SUPERQUMAP team, collecting researchers with different skills and background, is perfectly suited to disseminate the great potential of quantum technology. The numerous small companies and start-ups that are emerging from universities and research institutes will be interested to join the activities of SUPERQUMAP. In turn, the results of this Action will support the increasing number of companies revolving around quantum computation. These include, but are not limited to, companies addressing problems such as cooling devices (cryogenics) as well as those addressing the technology to read and manipulate superconducting qubits, device making companies as well as large companies that manufacture the needed electronics. SUPERQUMAP will boost the growth of these companies by providing international

connections, allowing them to showcase their results and channel their need for work requiring techniques that are not available to them.

The Action will set-up a dedicated group to involve the industrial stakeholders in the Action.

5.2 Citizens

Actions aimed at the valorization of the SUPERQUMAP project will be directed also to the civil society. The tools described in Section 3 will help in the communication of the Action results, in order to raise the awareness of the general public on the opportunities offered by the next quantum revolution. It will be important to communicate these results using the correct language. Scientific communication should use a language that is, on one hand, accessible to the general public and, on the other, accurate enough to convey the scientific ideas with precision.

5.3 Intellectual property

As usual, every collaboration will make a provision of Intellectual Property Rights following EU rules. The Action will also support the youngest researchers in the writing of patents, by inviting an expert to explain the process in some of the Action meetings.